

INSONNING O'Z SOG'LIG'IGA BO'LGAN MUNOSABATINING SHAXSIY PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Kirish: shaxsning o'z salomatligiga munosabatining individual-psixologik xususiyatlari ruhiy va ijtimoiy farovonlik holatidir. Shaxs jamiyat ishlab chiqarishining asosiy harakatlantiruvchi kuchi, ishlab chiqarish va boshqa ijtimoiy munosabatlarning subyekti hisoblanadi. Maqolada shaxs salomatligi dolzarbligi, salomatlikni ta'minlashning omil va sabablari, jamiyat rivojlanishi va taraqqiyoti uchun shaxs salomatligiga munosabatining individual-psixologik xususiyatlari uyg'unligi o'z ifodasini topgan.

Maqsad: shaxs salomatligi dolzarbligini, salomatlikni ta'minlashning omil va sabablarini hamda jamiyat taraqqiyoti uchun individual-psixologik xususiyatlar uyg'unligini tahlil qilish.

Materiallar va metodlar: tadqiqotda salomatlik psixologiyasi tamoyillari, ijtimoiy-psixologik so'rovnomalar va shaxsning motivatsion qadriyatlarini qiyosiy tahlil qilish metodlaridan foydalanildi.

Natijalar va muhokama: maqolada jamiyat rivojlanishi uchun shaxs salomatligiga munosabatning ahamiyati yoritilgan. oila, ota-ona va farzand o'rtasidagi munosabatlar shaxsning o'z salomatligi uchun mas'uliyatini shakllantiruvchi asosiy omillar ekanligi aniqlangan.

Xulosa: shaxs salomatligiga munosabatni psixologik xizmat orqali muvofiqlashtirish jamiyatda sog'lom ijtimoiy munosabatlar va motivatsion qadriyatlar barqarorligini ta'minlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: oila, jamiyat, salomatlik, salomatlik psixologiyasi, ruhiyat va salomatlik, psixologik xizmat, jamiyatda shaxslararo munosabatlar, ota-ona, farzand, motivatsiya, qadriyat, mas'uliyat.

ИНДИВИДУАЛЬНЫЕ ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ ОТНОШЕНИЯ ЧЕЛОВЕКА К СОБСТВЕННОМУ ЗДОРОВЬЮ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Введение: индивидуально-психологические особенности отношения человека к своему здоровью представляют собой состояние духовного и социального благополучия. Человек является главной движущей силой общественного производства, субъектом производства и других социальных отношений. В статье отражена актуальность личного здоровья, факторов и причин его обеспечения, а также гармоничность индивидуально-психологических

особенностей отношения человека к своему здоровью для развития и прогресса общества.

Цель: анализ актуальности здоровья личности, факторов и причин его обеспечения, а также гармонии индивидуально-психологических особенностей отношения к здоровью для развития общества.

Материалы и методы: в исследовании использовались принципы психологии здоровья, социально-психологические опросы и методы сравнительного анализа мотивационных ценностей личности.

Результаты и обсуждение: в статье освещена значимость отношения личности к здоровью для прогресса общества. установлено, что отношения в семье, между родителями и детьми, являются ключевыми факторами формирования ответственности личности за свое здоровье.

Заключение: координация отношения к здоровью через психологическую службу обеспечивает стабильность здоровых социальных отношений и мотивационных ценностей в обществе.

Ключевые слова: семья, общество, здоровье, психология здоровья, психика и здоровье, психологическая помощь, межличностные отношения в обществе, родители, дети, мотивация, ценности, ответственность

INDIVIDUAL PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF A PERSON'S ATTITUDE TO THEIR OWN HEALTH

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ANNOTATION

Introduction: individual-psychological characteristics of a person's attitude to his health are a state of spiritual and social well-being. A person is the main driving force of social production, a subject of production and other social relations. The article reflects the relevance of personal health, factors and reasons for ensuring health, the harmony of individual-psychological characteristics of a person's attitude to his health for the development and progress of society

Objective: to analyze the relevance of individual health, the factors and reasons for ensuring health, and the harmony of individual-psychological characteristics in health attitudes for social progress.

Materials and Methods: the study utilized principles of health psychology, socio-psychological surveys, and comparative analysis methods of individual motivational values.

Results and Discussion: the article highlights the importance of health attitudes for societal development. it was found that family relations, specifically between parents and children, are primary factors in shaping an individual's responsibility for their health.

Conclusion: coordinating health attitudes through psychological services ensures the stability of healthy social relationships and motivational values within society.

Keywords: family, society, health, health psychology, psyche and health, psychological service, interpersonal relationships in society, parents, children, motivation, values, responsibility.

A person living in society always lives under the influence of different groups, at different periods of ontogenesis, a person experiences and witnesses different life situations. The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 19.06.2023 No. PQ-196 "On measures to further develop the service for protecting the mental health of the population" is also aimed at strengthening the mental health of members of society. The individual-psychological characteristics of a person's attitude to his or her health (character, temperament, abilities) are manifested through the person's actions in activities aimed at maintaining his or her health, as well as personal responsibility. These individual-psychological characteristics of a person are distinguished by social adaptation in social relations, the person's level of well-being and satisfaction with his or her life, and the ability to self-manage in relationships.

The main individual-psychological structural aspects of a person's attitude to his health are as follows:

- Active positive attitude of a person: a person considers his health to be a high value, constantly adheres to a healthy lifestyle, and carries out his activities on the basis of measures (sports, proper nutrition).
- Passive attitude of a person: attention is paid to his health only when mental and physical illness occurs or when a serious danger threatens.
 - Irresponsible attitude: negligence in a person's attitude to his health, a tendency to harmful habits and an incorrect assessment of the body's capabilities. (Disturbance of psychological defense mechanisms).

Individual-psychological factors of a person are as follows.

1. Motivation of a person - the internal need to be healthy.
2. Temperament types: people with a high level of anxiety pay more attention to their health, while people with calm character traits are often more negligent about their health.
3. Personality traits also play a key role in maintaining health.

These characteristics of a person determine the qualities and characteristics of adaptation to the social environment and life expectancy. In ontogenesis, individuality is considered to be the sum of all the unique characteristics that distinguish a person from another person. If we analyze the individual-psychological characteristics of a person's attitude to his health, we can include the person's abilities, temperament, character, volitional qualities, emotions, motivation inherent in the person's behavior, and the person's social attitudes. An individual's individual approach to his health is, in fact, a stable psychological characteristic that determines a person's behavior in different conditions. Professor V.M. Karimova emphasizes this by saying, "A healthy lifestyle and mental health should become a natural and organic need for a person, which he must consciously and voluntarily adhere to throughout his life." In protecting his health, temperament types and individual

characteristics are of particular importance, as are the characteristics of personality types (introvert, extrovert). These characteristics have different effects on a person's health. Extroverted individuals are more socially active in various interpersonal relationships. A person's temperament determines not only the style of interaction, but also the tendency to certain types of relationships with health. Choleric individuals are more concerned about their health, while melancholic individuals think about their health in a calm and stable way, especially in maintaining their health, which ensures their success in self-management in various conditions. A person's personal individual characteristics affect the correct perception and interpretation of existing situations, as well as the strategy of behavior.

Research method: To determine the individual-psychological characteristics of a person's attitude to his own health, a number of methods and forms are used, allowing for data collection and comprehensive analysis.

Description of the current methods used:

Approval motivation assessment scale The assessment scale developed by D. Marlow and D. Crown is used to assess a person's attitude to his own health, individual-psychological characteristics, and a wide range of a person's attitude to his own health in various life situations.

Questionnaire on the attitude to one's own health: provides information about the attitude of individuals to their own health in various life situations, the role of health and mental health in the ontogenesis of a person;

The health attitude questionnaire is used to analyze a person's attitude to his own health. R.A. Berezovskaya: assesses the tendency of a person to perceive events occurring in various life situations as a result of his own actions or external factors, which positively affects his individual psychological characteristics.

S. Deryabo and B. Yasvin's "Health Attitude Index" consists of four subtests corresponding to the four components of the intensity of the subjective attitude towards health, and the scales study the attitude of a person to his or her health in different situations. As a result of our observations, statistical and qualitatively analyzed data were obtained. The results of the analysis revealed the following. When studying the individual-psychological characteristics of the respondents' attitude to their own health, they showed different characteristics. While the majority of participants were found to be compatible with the choleric, melancholic, sanguine, and phlegmatic types (in 1st-year students), the majority of respondents studying at higher levels showed a predominance of types characteristic of the phlegmatic type. The clarity of individual characteristics such as benevolence, responsibility, and honesty was observed in the behavior and character traits of the participants. Especially in various life situations, a person's attitude towards his health is rational in nature, which does not greatly affect his emotional sphere. Taking care of his health is simply a necessity, but it is not considered a joyful and exciting activity.

It was found that the influence of personal psychological characteristics on the health of the individual is significantly high. Based on the individual characteristics of the respondents, the following was determined. Representatives of the choleric and sanguine types are distinguished by their greater tendency to social interaction. Phlegmatic and

melancholic, on the contrary, showed more stable, but less diverse social relationships. Personal characteristics such as honesty and benevolence are reliable and long-term and are considered the main characteristics in ensuring the health of the individual. Conflict in the personality negatively affects the health of the individual in interpersonal relationships, leading to the disruption of positive relationships. Individual psychological characteristics of the individual significantly determined the method of influence on health. During our observations, it was found that the high level of emotional intelligence of the respondents helps them take care of their own health. It was found that people with a high level of emotional intelligence have good skills in managing their emotions and resolving conflicts, which indicates that the person is highly attentive to their own health. The above characteristics and circumstances emphasize the importance of emotional intelligence in forming and maintaining healthy psychological relationships in a person. According to V.M. Karimova, who has studied the socio-psychological essence of psychology for many years, "The issue of the socio-psychological image of a person is also an extremely important area in today's era of changes and spiritual purification. After all, the attitude of each person to the fundamental reforms taking place in society, the level of their perception and understanding, the nature of their attitude towards themselves, social motives and directions in their behavior are of great importance. Especially in the process of a child's socialization, that is, his entry into the environment of social relations, his absorption of social influences into his consciousness and the strengthening of one or another type of behavioral patterns, the formation of an ideological worldview, it is necessary to examine the psychological nature of the processes of his socialization in the process of adulthood in order to create a program for raising a well-rounded person. However, since this process occurs in each person in his own way, his social types are distinguished in social psychology, and it is of practical importance for each coach or educator to know them. mass phenomena are also of practical importance for social psychology. Because denying the influence of mass phenomena and large groups in the upbringing of an individual is tantamount to a one-sided approach to the issue. For example, for an individual, the spirit of the nation, people or people to which he belongs, such as the traditions, images, beliefs, customs, and stereotypes of activity that have been preserved in his mind for centuries, has its own specific influence. The spirit of the nation is formed in the family environment through the national language that he has mastered in early childhood. [46;10]. Our observations confirmed the high importance of individual psychological characteristics in protecting a person's health.

During our observations, it is important to test the reliability of the results of the questionnaire on personal health in practice. Therefore, the questionnaire "A person's attitude to his own health" was used to study personal health. With the help of this questionnaire, we tried to study the participation of students of higher educational institutions in Samarkand, Fergana, Surkhandarya, Jizzakh, Syrdarya, Tashkent (a total of 970 people). With the help of this questionnaire, the person's attitude to his own health, mental and physical health, and individual characteristics were described in the questions.

The answers to each scale of the questionnaire are presented in different options. They express the individual's individual psychological characteristics and the level of their development. In managing personal health, more external factors are influenced and in adverse situations, he gets into a difficult situation, gets nervous and experiences a feeling of anxiety. These personal circumstances cannot but affect effective functioning in various life situations.

"Do you feel healthy when you are in a good mood?" 97.3% of respondents emphasized that health is related to the psyche, and that a person's attitude to their health is related to individual psychological characteristics, while 2.7% stated that they think there is no connection. During our separate interviews with the respondents, we explained that a person's psyche and health are in harmony and outlined our relevant recommendations.

"How much do you care about your health?" 91.0% of respondents stated that they often worry, 8.0% said that they do not feel the need to do so because they are healthy, 1.0% said that they do not want to make material expenses, and we gave clear recommendations that a healthy person constantly has a worthy impact on the development of society, and first of all, a person's mental and physical health is one of the main aspects of a person's health.

"What do you do when you feel mentally tired and sick in your body?" 93.1% of respondents said that they go to the doctor to improve their health and improve their activities, 29% said that they take decisive measures to solve the problems that have arisen in their health due to various life situations, personal health is above all, 2.3% said that they think it is necessary to ignore it, 1.7% of respondents said that they constantly consult with those around them about their health. We have outlined our relevant recommendations on the importance of protecting a person's mental and physical health in their activities. "What do you do to maintain health in various situations in social life?" 97.7% of respondents stated that it is necessary to always pay attention to their mental and physical health, 1.2% of respondents stated that due to various life circumstances, they are unable to pay attention in time, and 1.1% of participants stated that they pay attention extremely strongly, which is why instability in the individual's mood and susceptibility to external influences in self-assessment were observed.

"Do you take any measures to maintain your physical and mental health?" During our observations, participants responded on several scales. 82.7% said that they follow a sleep and rest schedule, 1.2% of participants said that they protect themselves mentally from harmful habits, 2.1% said that they protect their mental and physical health by constantly monitoring their weight, and 14% of participants said that they follow dietary rules. A high level of anxiety was observed in various life situations. It is necessary to pay attention to one's mental and physical health when health deteriorates due to various life circumstances in social life. Being constantly demanding and persistent in relation to one's health in everyday life is a positive feature in ensuring one's health. One's health is important in various life circumstances, and health is extremely important not only for maintaining mental and physical health in various life circumstances, but also for maintaining mental and physical health. In his 44-chapter work, Kaykovus pays special

attention to personal upbringing and searches for the causes of psychological characteristics that occur in the human psyche. The work pays special attention to the behavior, actions, and character traits of young people, emphasizing the need for young people to always pay attention to the science of speech and eloquence from a young age. "Whenever you speak to the public, speak with a good face, so that it is acceptable and the public knows that you have a high status through your words. It is said that people can know a person's status by their words, but people cannot know the status of their words, because each person's condition is hidden under their words, that is, they can say a word with one voice, and the heart of the person who hears it will be dark (dark), and they can say the same word with one voice, and the soul of the person who hears it will be happy from it" [100]. Protecting health in interpersonal relationships, taking possession of the human mind and heart The prevention of various threats, the formation of immunity to psychological threats, and the spiritual and physical development of the individual remain among the most priority tasks. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev emphasized this: "Today, New Uzbekistan is boldly entering a new stage of its development. We have set ourselves ambitious goals that serve, first of all, human happiness and human dignity, because human happiness begins with the family, and the family is strong with a woman. The future generation will mature in this sacred space. At a time when the situation in the world is becoming dangerous, peace and tranquility in our country are a great blessing, and it is the sacred duty of each of us to deeply feel this and preserve it."

We believe that in order to achieve high efficiency in ensuring a person's mental and physical health, it is necessary to adhere to the following recommendations:

1. A person must have complete information about the conditions that ensure health in various life situations and be able to psychologically analyze various social relationships.
2. The person must not fall into depression in overcoming the difficulties encountered at different stages of ontogenesis, in achieving the goals of his activity, which ensures success.
3. We believe that it is necessary not to disclose mental problems in everyday life, in relationships with family and friends in various life situations.
4. Reading a lot of books related to physical health and personal psychology throughout a person's life will help to understand the purpose and overcome difficulties in social relationships.
5. We highly appreciate the need to pay attention to age and gender characteristics in maintaining mental and physical health.
6. The primacy of behavior, treatment and communication in ensuring a high level of personal health has been confirmed.
7. A person can ensure his mental and physical health by paying special attention to political, ethnic, religious and gender diversity in social relations.

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